

'I listen in different ways than others, but I am not mad, bad or dumb' - © Dr Damien Howard

People with normal hearing, who have good auditory and verbal skills, generally assume that others reach an understanding of what is said the same way as they do – by relying mainly on auditory skills. However, people with listening difficulties often understand what has been said in quite different ways. Because they cannot rely on their auditory skills they develop other non-auditory strategies to supplement the information that they can hear. These skills are most effective when dealing with familiar people in known situations, where the listener can use an existing framework of knowledge, or build one ahead of time, to guide their understanding. So already knowing about what is being talked about or pre-learning about what will be talked about in the future are often important ways to better understand what is said.

Familiarity with people, processes and with situations helps those with listening problems, because they can better anticipate what will be said and thus compensate for their listening difficulties. Many of these ways of listening rely more on thinking about and integrating what is seen, or has been seen in the past, with what is being heard.

'Thinking-listening' requires more mental effort so people tire more quickly than others in intensive listening situations. They may listen for a time, tire, then 'tune-out' and stop trying to listen. Also, people who rely on 'thinking-listening' skills generally need a break after listening for a time. Much of the thinking that helps understanding may actually happen after something has been heard - processing known information to integrate with what has just been heard. If people don't get enough processing time after listening, they may get frustrated and/or understand less. Also having some recovery time after intensive listening is important. Some quiet time to recover at the end of a day of heavy 'thinking-listening demands' is usually needed. Two people, one with good auditory skills and another who relies more on 'thinking-listening' skills, will leave a long listening session feeling very different. The person with good auditory skills may be relaxed and comfortable and keen to socialise. The person who has been working harder to understand what has been said may be exhausted and desperately in need of some quiet time without conversation. It is common that children with listening problems arrive home from school ready to have a tantrum from the pent up emotions and frustration of having worked so hard trying to listen at school. Similarly, an older person with listening problems may blow up at their partner when they try to keep talking to them on the way home from a social gathering, after they have become mentally exhausted from trying so hard to listen.

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WHAT'S YOUR STORY?

If you would like to share your experiences of living with APD please email your story to Aly apduknews@aol.com

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Dr Damien Howard is an Australian psychologist who has specialised in the psycho-social outcomes of listening problems (hearing loss and auditory processing problems). He is available for internet based consultations and can be contacted here: damien@phoenixconsulting.com.au

Adults with APD Research

The Adults with APD Research project with Dr Damien Howard, on which many ground-breaking articles for our newsletters have been based, will recommence in 2014 via online chats for adults. Details will be posted on our adult forums. Please take part! All information is used anonymously. Email for details. apduknews@aol.com

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Having a familiar topic being talked about and/or a familiar person listened to helps make people's thinking-listening skills most effective. When people have their own 'framework of knowledge' about what is talked about there is less need to think constantly. So there may be a preference to mostly engage with familiar people and avoid strangers - see the Adults with APD research article 'The trouble with Strangers', in APDUK newsletter 2.

Also it is easier to cope with listening when there are routines or when someone has control over what will happen. Being 'bossy' is one way to cope with listening problems. A teacher told a story about a student with listening problems who coped by being bossy.

Helen used to hassle him all the time about, "What's happening next? What are we doing next?" Finally he said to her, "Look, here's my timetable, just keep that under your desk and then you'll know what's happening." That was fine for about a week until one day he was running overtime in one lesson, and Helen came up and said, "Timetable says we should be doing maths now." He said, "Yeah, we'll get to that. Don't worry about it." She said, "No. Hey, you all, pack up, we're doing maths now." She then organised the rest of the group to pack up and go on to maths. Helen took control to maintain his plans. When the teacher didn't follow routine, she acted to take control of the situation herself. She was seeking predictability. For people who have listening problems, predictability is often important. It reduces the need to listen in order to know what to do. If they know what is going to happen they are able to prepare themselves to cope. One way of creating predictability is to control social dynamics (be bossy) and so better manage listening demands.

When it is challenging to listen - for example, when it is noisy, or the topic is unfamiliar, or there are limited visual cues, then people with listening problems have to work harder. They may get more stressed or may respond by avoiding the situation or by being more bossy. These challenges are mostly invisible to those with good listening skills, so these kinds of responses by those with listening problems may be perplexing and irritating. Those displaying them are liable to be seen negatively as 'mad, bad or dumb'. Those with listening problems see these judgments, since being visually astute is a common compensatory strategy that is developed. When repeated over many years with different people those with listening problems may come to believe these judgments about themselves. After all, they so many people believing the same thing about them can't be a coincidence. While it isn't a coincidence, the judgments are not true. Understanding the processes that prompt these inaccurate judgments is important to avoid others beliefs becoming self-fulfilling.

This is important for both those with listening problems and those around them. Those with listening problems will mostly not realise how the challenges of listening have contributed to who they are. They are liable to think that they must be not be as smart as others because they struggle understanding what others grasp easily. They usually do not know they are working much harder than others in getting to understanding what has been said. Or, they may feel confused and ashamed when they don't understand what has been said as well as others do. They often don't understand why they experience the frustration and stress they do, or may try to avoid, tune out or boss others in certain situations. Understanding what is happening is often an important step for people to cope with situations better, feel less self-critical about themselves and to protect themselves from the potential toxic effects of other people's judgments.

Understanding these processes is also important for those who live with, are friends of, or work with those with listening problems. Understanding what people with listening problems experience - and why they do certain things - helps establish more co-operative and positive relationships. It is especially important for parents to help children to deal with their feelings about others' judgments and it is often necessary to act as an advocate with some teachers who may make destructive judgments about kids being 'mad, bad or dumb'